

e-ISSN: 2584-2218

**Volume 09 Issue 01
Jan-Apr 2026**

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**Submission Date : Dec
31, 2025**

**Copyright Received
Date: Jan 3, 2026**

Comparative Study of Woven and Non- Woven Geotextiles Using CBR

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ABSTRACT

Geosynthetics are man-made geotextile fibres that provide high performance and long-term solution to challenges in geotechnical works. This study aims to discuss the potential of using polypropylene woven and non-woven geotextiles as reinforcement to weak soil and thereby improving the bearing capacity and making it more durable for construction projects. The main aim is to compare the effect of woven and non-woven geotextiles on soil stabilization using controlled laboratory test and verifying and analysing their impact. Specific gravity, Grain size distribution, Atterberg Limit tests are performed to determine the basic index properties of the three different soil samples. Modified Proctor Test (to determine OMC and MDD) and California Bearing Ratio (CBR) tests were conducted on unreinforced soil sample and reinforced soil sample with polypropylene woven and non-woven geotextiles. For the CBR test the geotextile was placed at three different heights of the mould: at the bottom of the mould, at mid height of the mould and at 1/3rd height from top of the mould in a single layer for three different soil samples. The results indicate improvement in the CBR value of soil sample with woven geotextile giving higher CBR value than non-woven geotextile. On the other hand, there is a different trend for the granular sub-base soil sample (GSB) as the geotextiles tends to get puncture. The study also showed woven textile works best when placed at bottom of the mould and non-woven works best when placed at 1/3th height from the top of the mould. Therefore, from our study, woven geotextiles are a more suitable option for long-term soil reinforcement applications due to their superior durability and sustained mechanical performance.

Keywords: Geosynthetics, geotextiles, polypropylene woven geotextile, non-

woven geotextile, California bearing ratio (CBR), soil reinforcement

INTRODUCTION

The strength and stiffness of subgrade soil play a critical role in determining pavement performance. Weak soils often lead to excessive deformation, cracking, and reduced service life of pavements. Improving subgrade properties is therefore essential, especially in regions dominated by clayey soils.[1,6,7]

Geosynthetics have gained widespread acceptance as soil reinforcement materials due to durability, ease of installation, and cost effectiveness. Among them, geotextiles provide reinforcement through tensile resistance, membrane action, and improved confinement. Woven geotextiles

possess high tensile strength, making them suitable for reinforcement applications, whereas non-woven geotextiles offer better filtration and separation but lower tensile capacity.[8,9]

The effectiveness of geotextiles reinforcement depends on soil type, geotextile characteristics, and placement depth. Although several studies have examined geotextiles-reinforced soils, comparative evaluation of woven and non-woven geotextiles at different placement levels using CBR testing remains limited. This study addresses this gap through a controlled laboratory investigation.[2,10,11]

LITERATURE REVIEW

Authors and Years	Soil type	Geotextile type	Key observations on CBR improvement	Inference on Geotextile Type
Negi and Singh (2020)[14]	Clayey and sandy soil	Woven and non-woven	Significant CBR increase in weak clayey soil	Woven consistently outperformed non-woven due to higher tensile strength
Gautam et al. (2020)	Soft clay and aggregate	Woven, Non-woven, Geogrid	Woven gave higher CBR than Non-woven Geogrid= woven gave maximum improvement	Woven better than non-woven, composite systems most effective
Thakur et al. (2021)[17]	CH clay	Non-woven	CBR increased with increase in geotextile thickness up to optimum	Non-woven improves CBR, but effectiveness depends on thickness and bonding

MATERIALS

Soil Samples

Three soils were selected for the study. High plastic clay (CH) was collected from Dergaon tea Estate, Assam. Granular sub-base (GSB) material was obtained from

also Dergaon. Intermediate plastic clay (CI) was collected from Lahdoigarh, Assam. The soils were Classified based on grain size distribution and Atterberg limits.[3,12,13]

Fig. 1: Soil Sample- 1, Site- Dergaon.

Fig. 2: Soil Sample- 2, Site- Dergaon.

Fig. 3: Soil Sample- 3, Site- Lahdoigarh.

Geotextiles

Polypropylene woven and non-woven geotextiles were used as reinforcement materials. The woven geotextile exhibited higher tensile strength and lower thickness,

non-woven geotextiles was thicker but comparatively weaker in tension. These difference significantly behaviour during CBR testing.[4,14]

Table 1: Properties of woven and non-woven geotextiles.

Geotextile type	GSM	Thickness (mm)	Tensile strength (kn/m)
Woven	110	0.5	18
Non-woven	120	0.9	7.5

METHODOLOGY

Laboratory testing was performed in accordance with IS 2720 specifications. Grain size analysis, Sieve analysis and Atterberg limit tests were conducted to determine soil classifications and plasticity

characteristics. Modified Proctor Compaction tests were carried out to obtain optimum moisture content (OMC) and maximum dry density (MDD) of each soil.[5,15]

Table 2: Index properties of all three soil samples.

Basic Index Properties	Soil Sample 1	Soil Sample 2	Soil Sample 3
Soil type	CH Soil (High Plasticity Clay)	GSB (Granular Soil)	CI Soil (Medium Plasticity Clay)
Specific Gravity	2.25	-	2.35
Liquid Limit	72%	-	35.05%
Plastic Limit	19.67%	-	22%
Plasticity Index	52.33%	-	13.05%
Maximum Dry Density (MDD)	4.65 g/cc	4.57 g/cc	4.47 g/cc
Optimum Moisture Content (OMC)	14.20%	5.52%	5.63%

Unsoaked CBR tests were conducted on both unreinforced and reinforced soil specimens. For reinforced soil samples, a single layer of geotextile was placed at the following positions within the CBR mould:

- Bottom of the mould
- Mid-height of the mould
- 1/3rd height from the top of the mould

All specimens were compacted at their respective OMC and MDD. Load vs penetration curves were recorded, and

CBR values were calculated at penetrations of 2.5mm and 5mm.[16]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental results show that geotextile reinforcement significantly improves the CBR values of clayey soils. When woven geotextiles consistently produced higher CBR values compared to non-woven geotextiles due to their higher tensile strength and effective stress redistribution. In table 5.1 the CBR values of unreinforced and reinforced soil samples are provided.

Fig. 4: Comparison of curves for CBR values among unreinforced, woven and non-woven geotextile reinforcement at the bottom of the mould for soil sample 1.

Fig. 6: Comparison of curves for CBR values among unreinforced, woven and non-woven geotextile reinforcement at 1/3rd height from the top of the mould for soil sample 1.

Fig. 6: Comparison of curves for CBR values among unreinforced, woven and non-woven geotextile reinforcement at the bottom of the mould for soil sample 3.

Fig. 7: Comparison of curves for CBR values among unreinforced, woven and non-woven geotextile reinforcement at 1/3rd height from the top of the mould for soil sample 3.

The maximum improvement was observed when the geotextile was placed at the bottom of the mould. At this position, the geotextile effectively acted as a tensioned

membrane, restricting vertical deformation and enhancing load distribution.

Non-woven geotextile demonstrated improved performance when placed at 1/3rd height from the top of the mould.

This placement allowed better interaction with the active stress zone, resulting in moderate CBR enhancement.

In case of GSB material, the inclusion of geotextiles led to a reduction in CBR

values. This behaviour was attributed to puncture and tearing of geotextiles caused by angular aggregates, which reduced effective reinforcement and shifted the failure mechanism to the granular layer.

Table 3: Comparison of CBR values of unreinforced and reinforced soil samples.

		CBR value (%)								
Geotextile type	Penetration (mm)	Soil sample 1 CH soil (high plasticity clay)			Soil sample 2 Granular soil (GSB)			Soil sample 3 CI soil (medium plasticity clay)		
		At bottom	At mid-height	At 1/3 rd height from top of the mould	At bottom	At mid-height	At 1/3 rd height from top of the mould	At bottom	At mid-height	At 1/3 rd height from top of the
None (unreinforced soil)	2.5	4.52			69.7			4.09		
	5	4.47			61.9			3.89		
Woven	2.5	21.75	17.44	16.05	15.62	26.86	25.32	20.65	17.3	14.45
	5	21.11	16.78	15.52	14.32	24.96	24.86	20.29	17	14.01
Non-woven	2.5	5.18	8.17	14.4	23.72	29.41	45.62	8.02	8.9	11.97
	5	4.72	7.98	13.47	22.96	28.95	44.33	7.93	8.85	11.82

Table 4: Placement wise analysis of woven and non-woven geotextiles.

Geotextile Type	Placement Position	CBR value trend	Observed behaviour	Soil-geotextile interaction	Best placement
Woven	Bottom	Highest	Maximum improvement in penetration resistance	Efficient stress redistribution over larger area	Bottom
	Mid-height	Moderate	Partial improvement in penetration resistance	Limited membrane action	
	1/3 rd height from top of the mould	Lowest	Less effective	Poor stress interception	
Non-woven	Bottom	Lowest	Minimal improvement	Ineffective confinement	1/3 rd height from top of the mould
	Mid-height	Moderate	Partial improvement	Limited frictional resistance	
	1/3 rd height from top of the mould	Highest	Significance resistance to penetration	High interlocking with soil particles	

CONCLUSION

Based on our study we see significant improvement in the CBR value of weak subgrade soil when we reinforced it with woven and non-woven geotextiles at different depths. There is also prominent difference between the CBR value enhance by woven and non-woven geotextile. Woven geotextiles provide greater improvement than non-woven geotextiles due to higher tensile strength. Placement of woven geotextiles at the bottom of the mould gives highest CBR value for subgrade soil. Non-woven geotextiles perform best when placed at 1/3rd height from the top of the mould which lies near the active stress zone of the CBR loading. However, geotextile reinforcement is ineffective for soil sample 2 which is a granular sub-base due to puncture failure.

FUTURE SCOPE

In the future further geotechnical tests which include direct shear test and triaxial tests can be performed to determine how strong and durable this material can be for long term improvement. The study can further be expanded by using geotextile in multilayer to see the changes in the CBR value. Also studying the environmental consequences of these geotextiles will provide us with the insights of choosing the suitable reinforcing element that are not only productive but also sustainable.

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